

Clinical Image

Fortuitous detection of extensive gutta-percha extruded into the maxillary sinus during root canal treatment on the 2nd upper left molar

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Abstract

Close proximity between the maxillary teeth roots and the maxillary sinus can lead to an unintentional deposition of endodontic obturation materials into the latter. Among these materials, the injectable thermoplasticized gutta-percha as a consequence of overfilling. In this report, a case of extensive gutta-percha extruded into the maxillary sinus during root canal treatment on the 2nd upper left molar is presented.

Keywords: Maxillary sinus, gutta-percha, root canal treatment.

Case presentation

A healthy 40-year-old woman presented for dental check up. On panoramic radiograph we noticed extreme overextension of gutta-percha within the maxillary sinus after endodontic treatment on tooth #27 (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Radiograph showing extensive gutta-percha extruded into the maxillary sinus

The patient revealed having undergone root canal treatment two months before and being completely symptoms free.

Further radiological investigations (three-dimensional imaging / CBCT) are scheduled in order to elaborate the adequate treatment plan.

References

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